

Macro-Economic Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Indian Economy

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Abstract

This article evaluated the macro-economic impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on India's Gross Domestic Product by considering Gross Fixed Capital Formation (GFCF) by Public and Private sector as the proxy indicator for AI. The analysis reveals that the contribution made by GFCF of private sector in GDP (20 per cent) is relatively higher than the share of GFCF of public sector in GDP (10 per cent) during the period 1950-51 to 2015-16. The correlation matrix indicated high degree of association between the GFCF by Public and Private sector and increasing growth rates of GDP in India. The regression analysis predicted that India's GDP is going to increase by 12.1 per cent by 2020 due to the increased investment on aggregate GFCF in India. Furthermore, the recent proposed policy in the India's budget of 2018-2019 related to Government's intervention in the emerging areas of AI will go a long way in ensuring better prospects and better future by boosting job growth, productivity and GDP for Indian economy.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Gross Domestic Product, Gross Fixed Capital Formation, Labour-intensive and Capital-intensive technologies

Introduction

Indian economy is one of the fastest developing countries of the world. The Census statistics reveal that 72 per cent of the people are dependent on agriculture and allied activities and it was followed by 10.6 per cent across industries and 17.3 per cent across the service sector during 1951. Over the period of time, there is gradual transformation across these sectors. Later in 2011, it is observed that the share of labour across agriculture sector have declined by 20.9 points and have increased across industries and services by 11.6 points and 9 points respectively. Further the agriculture sector contributes only 15 per cent to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) even though it grabs highest labour share relatively across the sectors. On the other hand, the service sector holds only 26.7 per cent of labour share but contributes the highest share in GDP i.e., 59 per cent. Similarly, the industrial sector contributes 26 per cent in GDP by holding 22.1 per cent of the labour share.

It therefore clearly indicates that there is gradual shift from labour intensive technologies to capital intensive technologies. It helps in increasing the level of investment in the various sectors by increasing

the quantity of the income-generating capital assets, thereby increasing productivity of the sectors. Furthermore, capital-intensive sectors are contributing more towards the growth of GDP and are often referred as “Engine of Growth”. The major reason that can be attributed to such gradual shift is the invention of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Digitalisation. In earlier days, the concept of Artificial Intelligence was more or less restricted only across Computer Science and mechanical engineering sectors. But gradually it is now transcending across each and every socio-economic sector and is transforming them into more capital-intensive sectors. Therefore, there is need to understand the impact of AI.

Literature Review

Nilsson (1984) analysed the influence of AI on employment and distribution of income. It has deeply dealt with the work eliminating consequences of AI which reduces the labour toil in the economy. Aghion et.al., (2017) examined the potential impact and implications of Artificial Intelligence on economic growth. It attempted to analyse the linkages between AI and economic growth by integrating production, marketing of goods, technology for new ideas and automation in capital share dynamics. Lee et.al., (2017) evaluated the potential economic benefits of AI on Ireland economy in 2030 and concluded that AI helped Ireland in boosting productivity, product enhancements, consumption-side enhancements and economic opportunities. Some of recent studies conducted namely Gilham et.al., (2018) and Basu et.al., (2018) have analysed the present and future impact of AI across socio-economic sectors namely agriculture, industry, education, health, financial services, security and defence, public utility, consumer and retail services in Indian economy.

Objectives of the Study

On the similar lines of the articles and reports reviewed in the previous sections, this article tries to evaluate the macro-economic impacts of AI with regard to Indian economy and it also tries to project the future economic growth in terms of GDP by considering Artificial Intelligence as the major driving factor contributing towards increase in economic growth of Indian economy.

Brief History of AI

The emergence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) can be witnessed with the advent of digital computers in 1950s. The actual initiation of AI can be traced back to 1956 by John Mc Carthy who is considered to be the Father of AI. Later on, the development of AI was carried by prominent persons namely John von Neumann, Alan Turing, Emil Post, Stephen Kleen and others. The concept of AI refers to branch of science involving the use and application of machines to carry out the activities of human. The major components of AI include Assisted Intelligence and Augmented intelligence with human intervention on one hand and on the other hand include Automated Intelligence and Autonomous Intelligence without human intervention. It works in line with the aspects namely machine learning, deep learning, logical reasoning, voice recognition, robotics, algorithms, navigation, remote sensing, decision making, collaborative and adaptive systems.

Results and Discussion

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become one of the significant component in enhancing the quality of capital intensive technologies. It has become an integral part of the planning process in such a way that in order to fulfil the socio-economic objectives of five-year plans, the AI technologies have been integrated along the socio-economic sectors. The recent AI technologies

in Indian market include Smart drones for digital farming, autonomous tractors, fleet of agribots for fertilisation and harvesting, image recognition softwares for crop-monitoring and prediction of farm yields, Machine learning, CCTV cameras, bio-metrics, diagnostics services, robotics in industries and service sector etc. With its various technical innovations involving digitization, it is going to transform and dominate the rapidly growing market in India leading to growth in output and employment. There is debate by the researchers that AI will replace human labour leading to unemployment, but one of the recent report of FICCI and NASSCOM titled “Future of Jobs in India” in December 2017 has predicted that “AI will create 2.3 million new jobs while eliminating only 1.8 million jobs till 2020. Further in 2021, AI augmentation will generate 2.9 trillion dollars in business value and will recover 6.2 billion hours of worker productivity.” Therefore, AI is going to have better emerging prospects and better future by increasing GDP and per-capita income.

GDP is an important indicator to assess the macro-economic growth of any country. The increase in GDP depends upon various factors namely employment, Gross value added, investment, consumption, savings, technology etc. Analysis rests on the basic classical assumption of *Ceteris Paribus* principle which states “Other things being equal”. In this regard, it is assumed that out of the various factors determining GDP growth, Artificial Intelligence is the only major driving factor contributing towards growth of GDP in Indian economy”. Since expenditure on AI in India is not available, Gross Fixed Capital Formation (GFCF) is used as a proxy indicator to analyse the impact of AI on the growth of GDP in India (See Table 1). It refers to the measure of value for existing and new capital stock leading to income generation. It is also termed as Net Investment as it does not include the depreciation charges of capital assets and purchase of land.

During the period 1950 to 2010, the aggregate expenditure on GFCF in India has seen tremendous increase from Rs. 968 crores in 1950-51 to that of Rs.2407069 crores in 2010-11 with Compound Annual Growth rate of 13.92 per cent. During the period 2000 to 2010, the aggregate expenditure has risen by 18.10 per cent. Since 2010, there is greater surge in the expenditure on GFCF by both public and private sector in India owing to the growth of AI in India. Further in the year 2015-16, the GFCF expenditure stood at Rs. 4002781 crores. Chart 1 presents the composition of GFCF by public and private sector in the total. During the year 1950-51, the share of private GFCF in the total was high as compared to that of the share of public GFCF in the total. Before the initiation of economic reforms in India, the ratio of public and private GFCF was 43:57. After the economic reforms of 1991 in India, the share of private GFCF in the total has seen drastic increase. Further in 2015-16, the ratio of public and private GFCF stood at 24:76.

Table 1 Gross Fixed Capital Formation in India

Year	Amount of GFCF (Rs. in crore)			Share of GFCF in GDP (in per cent)		
	Public	Private	Total	Public	Private	Total
1950-51	264	704	968	2.5	6.8	9.3
1960-61	1215	1075	2290	6.8	6.0	12.8
1970-71	2742	3746	6488	5.8	7.9	13.6
1980-81	13656	13159	26815	9.1	8.8	17.9
1990-91	60013	79650	139663	10.2	13.6	23.8
2000-01	145973	349223	495196	6.7	16.0	22.7
2010-11	609189	1797881	2407069	7.8	23.1	30.9
2011-12	641260	2356472	2997733	7.3	27.0	34.3

2012-13	698031	2626943	3324973	7.0	26.4	33.4
2013-14	796950	2718671	3515621	7.1	24.2	31.3
2014-15	833225	2950612	3783837	6.7	23.7	30.4
2015-16	1008535	2994247	4002781	7.4	21.9	29.3

Source: Derived from Economic Survey of India 2017-2018

During 1950-51, the share of aggregate GFCF in GDP stood at 9.3 per cent. It has seen gradual increase over the years. Since 1990-91, it has contributed more than 20 per cent in GDP. Further in 2015-16, it has stood at 29.3 per cent. Sector-wise contribution reveals that on an average the share of private sector's GFCF is quite high when compared to the share of public sector's GFCF. Since 2010, the share of private sector's GFCF in GDP has crossed 20 per cent in India whereas the share of public sector's GFCF in GDP has not crossed 10 per cent of GDP (See Table 1 and Chart No.2).

Table 2 Correlation Matrix between GFCF and GDP

	Public GFCF	Private GFCF	Total GFCF	GDP
Public GFCF	1	0.991	0.995	0.997
Private GFCF	0.991	1	1	0.995
Total GFCF	0.995	1	1	0.997
GDP	0.997	0.995	0.997	1

Note: Coefficient values are significant at 0.01 level of significance

Source: Author’s calculations

Correlation matrix reveals that there is very high degree of positive correlation between the GFCF of both public and private sector with Gross Domestic Product. The correlation co-efficient values are higher than 0.990 and are highly statistically significant at 0.01 level of significance with 99 per cent confidence interval. Higher is the level of GFCF, higher will be the GDP level of the economy. Comparative outlook between public and private GFCF reveals that the correlation between GFCF incurred by the public sector and to that of the GDP in Indian economy is relatively highest with 0.997 as against the value of 0.995 in case of private GFCF and GDP. (See Table 2).

Simple regression analysis is used to forecast the future GDP of Indian economy by 2020 with aggregate Gross Fixed Capital Formation as the factor to determine GDP. The expected Total GFCF in 2020 is around Rs. 7595440 crore which is projected using Compound Annual Growth Rate.

The regression equation estimated is

$$Y = a + bX$$

$$GDP = 111291 + 3.18 * \text{Total GFCF.}$$

$$GDP = 111291 + 3.18 * 7595440$$

$$GDP = 24229365 \text{ crores}$$

Therefore, the predicted GDP for the year 2020 is likely to be Rs. 24229365 crores. It is likely to increase by 12.11 per cent from Rs. 13682035 crores in 2015-16.

Conclusion

It is evident from the analysis that the investment spent on AI in India is more across private sector as seen in comparison with the public sector’s investment on AI. Further the relative contribution of public sector and private sector’s GFCF in the GDP also reveals the similar trend wherein the contribution made by private sector is quite high. The correlation matrix also revealed that there is high degree of association between the increased adoption of AI and increasing growth rates of GDP in India. The regression analysis also predicts that the GDP is going to increase by 12.1 per cent in 2020 due to the increased investment on aggregate GFCF in India. Therefore, there are positive macro-economic impacts on the growth of GDP due to increased adoption of AI technologies.

Further the recent India’s budget of 2018-2019 has proposed Government’s intervention in the emerging areas of AI as the part of digitisation of India. The National Institution for Transforming India (NITI) Aayog under the chairmanship of Amitabh Kant has devised national strategy for AI. It proposes to set up CORE - Centre of Research Excellence for pursuing technology frontiers to maximise production possibilities and also ICTAI – International Centers of Transformational AI to promote application based research along with private sector collaboration. Therefore, Indian economy is expected to have better prospects due to emergence of AI technologies in the near future.

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